

NODES

Nord Ovest Digitale E Sostenibile

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

Geodatabase Structure

SPOKE 4 – DIGITAL INNOVATION TOWARD SUSTAINABLE MOUNTAIN

DELIVERABLE DN.3 - SUMMER

Version history

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Contents

NODES – NORD OVEST DIGITALE E SOSTENIBILE.....	1
<i>VERSION HISTORY</i>	<i>1</i>
GLOSSARY.....	3
GEODATABASE	4
INTRODUCTION	4
OBJECTIVES	5
DATA MODEL	5
RELATIONSHIPS	6
BENEFITS.....	6
CONCLUSION	6

Glossary

	Definition
Hub Coordinator (HC)	The Hub Coordinator represents the single point of contact for the implementation of the innovation ecosystem towards the MUR. It carries out the management and coordination activities of the innovation ecosystem, receives the fundings, verifies, and transmits to the MUR the reporting of the activities carried out by the Spoke and their affiliates.
National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP)	This document uses the Italian acronym for the NRRP, which is PNRR (Piano Nazionale della Ripresa e Resilienza)
Research Program Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the NODES project. The NODES will appoint the Research Program Manager. It refers to "Responsabile del Programma di Ricerca" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
NODES' Research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spoke, with the aim to promote and support applied research on topics consistent with the Intelligent Specialization Strategy, with the guidelines of the 2021-2027 partnership agreement scheme, with regional operational plans and regional and national research and innovation priorities. Although NODES' Spokes are concentrated on different themes, they will organize their activities and actions within a common framework – NODES' Booster Methodology
Spoke Coordinator	The University in charge of coordinating the Spoke's ecosystem. It refers to "Spoke" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
Spoke Data Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the monitoring and management of data generated at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Data Manager.
Spoke Partner	The entity associated to the Spoke Coordinator. It can be an Innovation Cluster, Competence Center, Research Center related to the Spoke's ecosystem and contributes to achieve objectives and impact under the Spoke' leadership and management. It refers to "soggetti affiliati" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione".
Spoke Project manager	The person who will be the responsible for the management, coordination and progress of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Project Manager.
Spoke research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spokes. The spoke will leverage a consolidated collaboration with leading private and public companies and will focus the applied research activity on technological domains and applications that can favour the integration of SMEs into new value chains.
Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager.
Spoke Stakeholders Committee (SC)	Consultation structure formed by relevant stakeholders (Government, universities, companies, civil society, third sector, etc.)
Spoke Thematic	General target focus and domain of the Spoke research.
Spoke Topics	Specific areas/lines of development within the Spoke.
Spoke Work Package Leader	At the Spoke level, Work Packages (WPs) will be organized by WP leaders, who will be responsible for performance evaluation and reporting.
Flagship Project	Main research project at the Spoke level with the goal of prototyping, testing, demonstrating the research activities towards higher TRLs.

Geodatabase

Introduction

A geodatabase is a spatial data management system that stores and manages geographic information. It is a collection of data, including feature classes, attribute tables, rasters, and topologies, that are organized into a logical structure.

Geodatabases can be used to store and manage a wide variety of geographic data, such as:

- Streets and roads
- Buildings and other structures
- Land use and cover
- Elevation and terrain data
- Natural resources, such as forests, water bodies, and minerals
- Demographic data, such as population and income

Geodatabases can be implemented in a variety of ways.

- **File geodatabases:** File geodatabases are stored as a collection of files on a disk drive or network server. They are portable and can be easily shared between users.
- **Enterprise geodatabases:** Enterprise geodatabases are stored in a relational database management system (RDBMS), such as Oracle or PostgreSQL. They can be accessed by multiple users concurrently and can be scaled to support large datasets.
- **Cloud-based geodatabases:** Cloud-based geodatabases are stored in a cloud computing platform, such as Amazon Web Services (AWS) or Microsoft Azure. They offer the scalability and flexibility of enterprise geodatabases, without the need to invest in and maintain hardware and software infrastructure.

Figure 1. Schema of the data collection process for the geodatabase.

Objectives

As depicted in Figure 1, the geodatabase structure for the digital twin implementation will be designed to support the following key objectives:

- **Monitoring and forecasting of water resources and energy productivity:** The geodatabase will store data from a variety of sensors and remote-sensing platforms, including ground observations, aerial and satellite data, and UAVs. This data will be used to develop and deploy forecasting tools for water availability, snowpack accumulation and melting, and energy production.
- **Integrated management of energy and water resources:** The geodatabase will store data on all aspects of the energy and water systems, including infrastructure, resources, and consumption. This data will be used to develop and deploy digital twins and other modeling tools to support integrated management of these systems.
- **Development and deployment of innovative energy and water management solutions:** The geodatabase will be used to develop and deploy a variety of innovative solutions, such as plug-and-play monitoring and optimization software, artificial intelligence-based energy management strategies, and smart grid solutions for integrating intermittent renewables.

Data Model

The geodatabase will be organized into the following feature datasets.

- **Water Resources:** This feature dataset will store data on all aspects of the water resources system, such as the following.
- **Hydrographic features:** Rivers, lakes, reservoirs, glaciers, etc.
- **Water infrastructure:** Dams, canals, pipelines, treatment plants, etc.
- **Water quality data:** Measurements of water quality parameters such as temperature, pH, turbidity, and nutrient levels.
- **Water usage data:** Measurements of water consumption by different users, such as agriculture, industry, and households.
- **Energy Resources:** This feature dataset will store data on all aspects of the energy resources system, such as the following.
- **Energy infrastructure:** Power plants, transmission and distribution lines, etc.
- **Energy production data:** Measurements of energy production from different sources, such as hydropower, solar, wind, and fossil fuels.
- **Energy consumption data:** Measurements of energy consumption by different users, such as industry, households, and transportation.

In addition to these two feature datasets, the geodatabase will also include a feature dataset for **Sensors and Remote Sensing Platforms**. This feature dataset will store data on the location, type, and configuration of all sensors and remote sensing platforms that are used to collect data on the water and energy resources systems.

Relationships

The following relationships will be established between the feature datasets.

- **Water Resources to Sensors and Remote Sensing Platforms:** This relationship will link water resources features to the sensors and remote sensing platforms that are used to collect data on those features.
- **Energy Resources to Sensors and Remote Sensing Platforms:** This relationship will link energy resources features to the sensors and remote sensing platforms that are used to collect data on those features.
- **Water Resources to Energy Resources:** This relationship will link water resources features to energy resources features that are dependent on those water resources. For example, a hydropower plant will be linked to the reservoir that supplies it with water.

Benefits

The geodatabase structure described above will provide the following benefits.

- **Improved data management:** The geodatabase will provide a central repository for all water and energy resources data, making it easier to manage and access this data.
- **Enhanced data integration:** The relationships between the feature datasets will enable data from different sources to be integrated and analyzed together. This will provide a more complete and holistic understanding of the water and energy resources systems.
- **Support for digital twin implementation:** The geodatabase will provide the data foundation for developing and deploying digital twins of the water and energy resources systems. Digital twins can be used to simulate the behavior of these systems under different scenarios, which can support decision-making and optimize system performance.

Conclusion

The geodatabase structure described above will provide a robust and flexible foundation for the digital twin implementation of the NODES research project on water and energy management in mountain areas (Spoke 4). The geodatabase will support the collection, storage, management, and integration of all relevant data, and it will provide the data foundation for developing and deploying digital twins of the water and energy resources systems.